

**CHALLENGES
AND LEGAL SUPPORT
OF THE ECONOMY IN THE CONDITIONS
OF DIGITALIZATION**

COLLECTION OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS

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C43 **Challenges** and Legal Support of the Economy in the Conditions of Digitalization : collection of scientific works. Kyiv : Publishing Lira-K. 2024. 128 p.

Gaps and conflicts in legal regulation of economic relations in the conditions of digitalization are highlighted. Attention is focused on challenges to legal regulation caused by the digitalization of the economy. Topical issues of various branches of law in the conditions of digitalization are presented.

The Collection is addressed to scientists, lecturers, practitioners, applicants for academic degrees and students.

Виклики та правове забезпечення економіки в умовах цифровізації : збірник наукових праць. – Київ : Видавництво Ліра-К, 2024. – 128 с. – англ. мовою

Висвітлено прогалини та колізії правового регулювання економічних відносин в умовах діджиталізації. Акцентовано увагу на викликах правовому регулюванню, що зумовлені цифровізацією економіки. Представлено актуальні питання різних галузей права в умовах цифровізації.

Для науковців, лекторів, практиків, здобувачів наукових ступенів та студентів.

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CITIZEN-GENERATED DATA IN AS OPEN DATA: LEGAL REGULATION FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DEVELOPMENT

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A set of training data is needed at the stage of development of artificial intelligence technologies. In the process of forming such training datasets, developers often face problems due to different regulatory regimes of data protection. For example, the processing of personal data requires the informed consent of the data subject. By combining training datasets, it is possible to fulfill the “specifically identified person” criterion. This means that by using different datasets and combining them in a training dataset for artificial intelligence, developers get a dataset that specifically identifies a person, and such datasets are subject to legal protection of personal data. To create images, texts, music, and videos in training data, developers need to obtain permissions and licenses from the owners of intellec-

tual property rights. Since training datasets use hundreds, perhaps tens of thousands, of individual objects protected by intellectual property laws, entering into tens of hundreds of license agreements for each such object would significantly complicate the development of the technology. In such a highly competitive environment as the development of artificial intelligence technologies, the rapid and legal collection of data to form training datasets is of paramount importance. Therefore, it is relevant to study the legal regulation of open data as data that can be legally obtained and used quickly and without excessive bureaucratic procedures as training data sets for the development of artificial intelligence technologies.

Public information in the form of open data can be freely used and disseminated. Any person may reproduce, publish, distribute, use, including for commercial purposes, in combination with other information or by incorporating it into their own product, with a mandatory reference to the source of such information [1].

Of all the discussed legal regimes of data protection, the use of public information in the form of open data in training datasets seems to be the safest and most legal for the purposes of artificial intelligence technology development.

The peculiarity of open data is that it is created and published by public information administrators. However, in today's globalized world, a huge amount of data is generated by users when they use various smart things and mobile applications in the course of their daily life. Some of this data is collected by companies that own technical devices (smart things) or mobile applications and is used by companies to change and improve their business models [2, p. 65]. The data collected in this way is protected as confidential or business information by private companies, and it is usually impossible to obtain such structured data sets in the public domain. Even if such private companies acquire the status of a Manager (e.g., they have a dominant position in the market, special or exclusive rights, or are natural monopolies), they are obliged to publish data on the terms of supply of goods, services and prices for them [1]. Of all

the discussed legal regimes of data protection, the use of public information in the form of open data in training datasets seems to be the safest and most legal for the purposes of artificial intelligence technology development.

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Such data is often readily available on companies' websites as part of their marketing strategy. Data about goods, services, and their prices are much less interesting for use in training datasets compared to data that companies receive from citizens who use their mobile apps or that they receive from smart things while using them.

There is a large institutional structure for publishing open data sets that can be freely used, including for commercial purposes, and for using this data in training datasets for the development of artificial intelligence, so it is important to investigate whether there are opportunities on Open Data Portals for publishing data not only by Data Managers but also by citizens themselves. Such a social model will allow removing private companies from the process of collecting citizen-generated data and making this data open and public for all interested parties.

The issues associated with the research of citizen-generated data are addressed in the works of the following scientists: O. Corcho,

J. Blanco, C. Morote, Simperl E. [3], A. Meijer, S. Potjer [4], A. Suman [5], M. Ponti, M. Craglia [6]. In their scientific works, they proposed categories of data, their characteristics of classification, and the scope of their collection (from volunteer initiatives to government policies on the use of citizen-generated data) [3 p. 10].

Among researchers, there is no single definition for the concept of “citizen-generated data (hereinafter CGD)”. In particular, there are the following views on this category:

- Data consciously created by people is open and available in the *public domain* [4].

- Citizen-generated resources that allow us to question the expert knowledge produced. By evaluating this data using critical thinking techniques, real alternative views on the same problem can be formed by citizens themselves. As a result, these data can be seen as a form of social protest and grounds for policy change [5].

- open data are essential for public administration, as their use will help to coordinate joint actions of stakeholders *to solve social problems* [6].

- Data that individuals or a community of citizens create to directly monitor or stimulate change in issues that concern them [7]. That is, as one of the tools for participating in public affairs management.

- Data that provides direct representation of their interests and is an alternative set of data compared to the data collected by governments and international organizations [3, p.8].

Thus, the concept of CGD is highly dependent on the context of the study and is described both through the information categories of “data”, “collection”, “processing” and the intellectual property category of “public domain”, as well as tools for direct citizen participation in public affairs, “solving issues that concern them”, “alternative views”. The concept of CGD is mixed with forms of participation in public affairs management and citizen science (crowdsourced science, volunteer data). To distinguish these related

categories from CGD, we will provide some essential features and examples.

For the legal regulation of CGD, the essential characteristics are as follows:

- data are generated by individual citizens, not by Data Controllers;

- data is generated by citizens in the course of their daily life through the use of various mobile applications and smart things;

- citizens have the opportunity to upload the necessary data sets to specially created modules on Open Data Portals;

- data sets are uploaded in machine-readable formats.

Crowdsourced science is characterized by the wide involvement of stakeholders to provide specifically defined data to be used in scientific research [8]. That is, the qualifying features of these data are as follows:

- the purpose of their collection is for scientific activities;

- a specific data topic (e.g., health).

Such cooperation can take various forms, such as the placement of specific data by any person on specially designated information resources. This is how the largest database of coronavirus symptoms, Covid 19 – called ZOE was created; or by involving individuals in collaboration with teams of scientists to generate new scientific knowledge.

The legal regulation of open data provides for the use of this data legally in training datasets for the AI technology development. It is necessary to supplement the national legislation with the category of “open data in the form of citizen-generated data”, allowing interested parties to post additional categories of data on the Open Data Portal. It will also remove private companies from the chain of data processing and use by providing the possibility to publish citizen-generated data independently, at their own discretion. Some categories of citizen-generated data can be used as feedback and alternative communication tools in the process of engaging citizens in the direct management of state or local affairs. Use this data for

scientific purposes, statistics and monitoring, and to supplement the data of SDG indicators..

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Наукове видання

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